

A new genus *Zenobiellina* for *Helix subrufescens* Miller, 1822 (Hygromiidae), with description of a new congeneric species from northern Spain

Un nuevo género *Zenobiellina* para *Helix subrufescens* Miller, 1822 (Hygromiidae), con la descripción de una nueva especie congénica del norte de España

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ABSTRACT

The generic name *Zenobiella* Gude & Woodward, 1921, is in current use only for *Helix subrufescens* Miller, 1822. However, it ought to be regarded instead as a synonym of *Monacha* Fitzinger, 1833. The new genus *Zenobiellina* is therefore proposed to provide an appropriate name. Following I.C.Z.N. Art. 23.9, *Zenobia* J.E. Gray, 1821 is declared a "nomen oblitum" and *Monacha* Fitzinger, 1833 a "nomen protectum" so that the prevailing usage in favour of the latter junior name will be maintained.

A hitherto unknown land-snail species of the family Hygromiidae collected from two localities on low ground in the northern Picos de Europa (Spain) is named as *Zenobiellina graminicola* sp. nov. It resembles *Z. subrufescens* in genital anatomy, but differs clearly in shell characters, with one additional whorl, narrower body-whorl and larger umbilicus. It may also differ in showing a clear preference for grassland habitats, whereas *Z. subrufescens* more often occurs in woodland. Since both species apparently occur in N. Spain, the range of *Z. subrufescens* needs to be reassessed.

RESUMEN

El nombre genérico *Zenobiella* Gude & Woodward, 1921 se utiliza actualmente solo para *Helix subrufescens* Miller, 1822. Sin embargo, ha de considerarse como un sinónimo de *Monacha* Fitzinger, 1833. Por lo tanto, se propone el nuevo género *Zenobiellina* para proporcionar un nombre correcto. Siguiendo el C.I.N.Z. Art. 23.9, *Zenobia* J.E. Gray, 1821 se declara un "nomen oblitum" y *Monacha* Fitzinger, 1833 un "nomen protectum" para que se mantenga el uso prevaleciente de este último nombre.

Una especie de caracol de la familia Hygromiidae, recolectada en dos localidades de baja altitud en el norte de los Picos de Europa (España) y hasta ahora desconocida, se describe como *Zenobiellina graminicola* sp. nov. Se asemeja a *Z. subrufescens* en la anatomía genital, pero difiere claramente en los caracteres de la concha, con una vuelta adicional, la última vuelta más estrecha y un ombligo más grande. También puede diferir en mostrar una clara preferencia por los hábitats de pastizales, mientras que *Z. subrufescens* ocurre con mayor frecuencia en bosques. Dado que ambas especies parecen ocurrir en el norte de España, el área de *Z. subrufescens* necesita ser reevaluado.

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INTRODUCTION

On 22nd May 2001 we collected two empty shells we could not identify in a rocky limestone gorge adjacent to the Desfiladero de la Hermida in the north-eastern part of the Picos de Europa, Prov. Cantabria, N. Spain. Subsequent examination suggested they might be of an undescribed species of Zonitidae, so we returned on 12th May 2011, to search extensively under large rocks, in ground litter, and in other sites typical for semi-subterranean zonitids, but found just one more empty subadult shell. However, renewed study of the microsculpture on these shells suggested their affinity was with the monotypic genus *Zenobiella* (Hygromiidae) instead of with Zonitidae, although they otherwise differed from *Z. subrufescens* (Miller, 1822) in having a thicker shell with more whorls and a conspicuously larger umbilicus compared to the tiny or concealed umbilical chink of that species. We also noticed that the then newly published book by CADEVALL & OROZCO (2016: 500) illustrated the undescribed taxon with good photographs of a shell (from Covadonga, Asturias Prov.), but treated it erroneously under the heading *Zenobiella subrufescens*, while giving a description in the text that more closely matches the latter species.

Returning to the same gorge in the Picos de Europa again on 6th July 2017, we initially commenced searching foliage of bushes and saplings which we knew to be the main habitat for *Z. subrufescens* in Great Britain and Ireland. This was completely unsuccessful, but examination of other niches revealed that the unidentified snail was locally plentiful on grasses and herbs away from trees on the slopes just above the valley floor. A sample of >50 was collected easily, but all were immatures no more than half adult size. The same afternoon we visited Covadonga in the north-western part of the Picos de Europa and quickly found many more immatures of the same snail, living in abundance on herb-rich grassland of pathside banks near the Santuario. In order to study the

genital anatomy, we returned again to the gorge beside the Desfiladero de la Hermida on 23rd October 2017 and again found many of the snails alive on grasses and herbs. Although larger than in July, almost all of them were still immature but a sample was collected. Dissection revealed that the largest snail of all was an individual with nearly mature genitalia, confirming that they were correctly placed in the genus *Zenobiella*. The present paper therefore describes and names the new species and compares it in detail with *Z. subrufescens* s. str. The latter is briefly redescribed to clarify its diagnostic characters, its published Spanish records are briefly reviewed and its generic allocation is reassessed because of nomenclatural problems.

Several good photographs on a website have since been reidentified by us as showing only the hitherto undescribed taxon, incorrectly labelled as *Z. subrufescens* and depicting snails from Prov. Cantabria and Prov. Asturias in N. Spain (e.g., by Alejandro PEREZ-FERRER, 2011). Recently, NEIBER, RAZKIN & HAUSDORF (2017: 174, fig. 3B) presented new molecular-phylogenetic data on Hygromiidae which showed with strong statistical support that the three specimens of *Zenobiella* they studied represent two separate clades. GenBank entries for these show the two specimens forming one clade are from Banagher Glen, Northern Ireland, whereas the single specimen forming the second clade is from the Basque Country of N. Spain (S. of Vitoria-Gasteiz). However, they did not present any data on morphology of those snails.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Grid references of localities were recorded in 2017 using a hand-held Garmin Etrex High Sensitivity device accurate to <5 m horizontally and vertically; those for collections from 2001-2008 mainly used a Garmin Etrex Summit accurate to <10 m horizontally but considerably less accurate for altitu-

dinal data; older data for Great Britain and Ireland are from specimen labels and based on use of local topographic maps. Snails were collected by direct searching or dislodged by tapping or shaking vegetation over sieves. Living snails were drowned in water overnight, then preserved in 80% i.m.s. (with a few kept in 96% eth.). Shell descriptions and dissections were made using Meiji RZ Series stereo-microscopes, with anatomical drawings prepared with assistance from a Meiji drawing tube and shell measurements were made using an eyepiece graticule.

Shell growth appears to be indeterminate in this genus, so measurements of shells are given only for a few large shells comparable to those where dissection showed mature genitalia, and possessing a firm rather than membranous peristome edge. Shell whorls were counted using the method described by KERNEY & CAMERON (1979: 13). Bodies for anatomical study were pulled from the shells after fixation in the 80% i.m.s. preservative. Genitalia were examined, described and drawn after they were dissected out of bodies. Proximal and distal in anatomical descriptions refer to the position in relation to the ovotestis (gonad).

Abbreviations

AB: maximum breadth of shell aperture;
AH: maximum height of shell aperture (measured perpendicular to AB);
B: breadth of sh;
bis: bodies in i.m.s.;
CGAH: Collection of G.A. and D.T. Holyoak;
Coll.: collected by;
DTH: D.T. Holyoak;
eth: 96% ethanol;
GAH: G.A. Holyoak;
H: height of sh;
I.C.Z.N. Art.: Article of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature published by the International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature;
i.m.s.: 80% industrial methylated spirit;
MNCN: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid;
n: sample size;
NMW.Z: National Museum of Wales, Cardiff, U.K.;
n.v.: original not verified;
sh shells;
spm: whole specimens;
U: maximum breadth of umbilicus;
U.T.M.: Universal Transverse Mercator map grid system;
field number of site.

TAXONOMIC PART & RESULTS

HYGROMIIDAE Tryon, 1866, Subfamily HYGROMIINAE Tryon, 1866
Tribe HYGROMIINI Tryon, 1866 (following NEIBER *ET AL.*, 2017: 173)

Zenobiellina n. gen.

Type species: *Helix subrufescens* Miller, 1822

Diagnosis: Shell dextral, mature at 7.1-9.7 mm breadth, depressed-conical to rounded-conical, with 4.4-6.2 whorls when mature. Aperture oval to broadly oval, with simple peristome. Umbilicus narrow to very narrow, or covered by reflected peristome edge. Shell thin to very thin and weakly calcified, whitish to light brown or brown. Periostracum lacking hairs, lustrous, with microsculpture of spiral grooves that may intersect riblets to give decussate pattern.

Distal genitalia with long penis, long epiphallus and long slender flagellum. Middle of vagina with two large dart sacs inside common sheath; four forked mucus glands insert on vagina just proximal to tips of dart sacs. Interior of distal vagina with large conical appendix ending in point that may reach external genital pore. Reservoir of bursa copulatrix elongate, extending proximally as long tapering appendix. Right ommatophore retractor muscle passes

through angle between distal penis and distal vagina.

This genus has a complicated nomenclatural history. GRAY (1821: 239) introduced, without a description, the name *Zenobia* with two originally included species, *Helix (Zenobia) corrugata* which is a *nomen nudum*, and a second species *Helix (Zenobia) bimarginata* [as *binarginata*] validly introduced with a reference to plate 6 figs 31-32 of DRAPARNAUD (1805) which therefore becomes the type species by monotypy. These figures represent the Hélice bimarginée *Helix carthusianella* Draparnaud, 1801 (currently *Monacha cartusiana* (O.F. Müller, 1774) in family Hygromiidae) of which *H. (Z.) bimarginata* is therefore a junior objective synonym. The name *Zenobia* Gray, 1821 is thus a subjective senior synonym of *Monacha* Fitzinger, 1833.

GUDE & WOODWARD (1921: 179) established *Zenobiella* as a “n. nov.” for *Zenobia* J.E. Gray, 1821 which they believed to be preoccupied by *Zenobia* Oken, 1815 [Lepidoptera] but cited a different type species *Helix subrufescens* Miller, 1822. *Zenobiella* is in current use for that species, but this contradicts I.C.Z.N. Art. 72.7 which states that the replaced name and replacement name “have the same name-bearing type despite (...) any different taxonomic usage of the new replacement name”. Accordingly, *Zenobiella* is also a synonym of *Monacha* and there is no appropriate name for the taxon comprising *Helix subrufescens* Miller, 1822 and the new species described herein. A new genus is therefore proposed above for these.

Clarification that *Zenobia* J.E. Gray, 1821 is a subjective senior synonym of

Monacha Fitzinger, 1833 potentially produces another problem: *Monacha* has more species currently recognised than any other genus within the Hygromiidae, so a change of its generic name to give priority to *Zenobia* would be troublesome. OKEN (1815) is a rejected work (I.C.Z.N., 1956) so the names therein do not compete for homonymy, hence contrary to GUDE & WOODWARD (1921: 179), *Zenobia* J.E. Gray, 1821 is not preoccupied and it is therefore available for zoological nomenclature. However, the I.C.Z.N. Art. 23.9 (Reversal of Precedence) allows *Zenobia* J.E. Gray, 1821 to be declared a “nomen oblitum” and *Monacha* Fitzinger, 1833 a “nomen protectum” so that prevailing usage will be maintained. This depends on both of the following conditions being satisfied:

Art. 23.9.1.1, that the senior synonym or homonym has not been used as a valid name after 1899 (which remains true despite a single instance of its misuse by TAYLOR 1916: 47, since he only misapplied it as *Hygromia (Zenobia) fusca* (Montagu), i.e. to a synonym of *Z. subrufescens* Miller, 1822; in the same work Taylor (*op. cit.*, Part 23, pp. 77, 78, 96) used *Theba* Risso in place of *Monacha*, without mentioning *Zenobia*), and,

Art. 23.9.1.2, “the junior synonym or homonym has been used for a particular taxon, as its presumed valid name, in at least 25 works, published by at least 10 authors in the immediately preceding 50 years and encompassing a span of not less than 10 years.” The 25 works required are listed in the Bibliography at the end of this paper, each of those involved being marked §.

Zenobiellina subrufescens (Miller, 1822) (Figs. 1E-G, 2C-D)

Helix fusca Montagu, 1803, Test. Brit., p. 424, pl. 13, fig. 1 (non Poiret, 1801).

Helix subrufescens Miller, 1822, *Annals of Philosophy* (N.S.), 3 (17), p. 379, no. 43. [Locality indicated only “In woods”, but subsequent authors have assumed the type locality was near Bristol, England, based on the title of the publication].

Material examined: Great Britain, W. Cornwall, 2 Dec. 2000, deciduous woodland, W. side of Bonython Plantation, SW694205, 8 sh; E. Cornwall: *14 May 1967, woodland bank near Treverbyn Bridge, SX2067, Coll. J.A. Paton (ex S.M. Turk Colln.), 1 sh; 16 Jan. 1999, edge of lane, ditch with banks and walls covered by *Hedera*, Polclose, SW95Q, 1 sh; 17 Jan. 1999, shaded disused railway cutting with

saplings, S. of Eglosayle, SX003713, 2 sh; 30 Jan. 1999, roadside bank / Cornish hedge, Talland Bay, SX25F, 1 sh; 28 Sept. 1999, sieved from *Pteridium* on banks alongside path, Red Moor N.R., W. of Tredinnick pits, SX073621, 2 sh; 10 Jan. 2000, sieved litter from *Corylus/Alnus glutinosa* coppice with *Chrysosplenium oppositifolium*, S. of Merry Meeting, SX 088722, 2 sh; 5 Nov. 2003, grassy bank at edge of reservoir, Upper Tamar Lakes, SS28921173, 16 sh; 8 Oct. 2007, on tall vegetation on bank / Cornish hedge along roadside, near Trehursey Bridge, SX299648, 20 sh + bis.

Ireland, S. Kerry, 13 May 2006, on ferns, Glanleam Gardens, Valencia Island, V40517737, 1 sh; S. Kerry, 29 Apr. 2008, from tree-fern litter in mature estate garden, Rossdohan, V714627, 6 sh; N. Kerry, 12 May 2005, mixed woodland on wet slopes by river, Torc Cascade, near Killarney, V966844, 3 sh; Co. Kilkenny, 4 Sept. 2005, on *Phragmites* along river, Jenkinstown Park near Ballyraffon, S491638, 1 sh; Co. Kilkenny, 6 Sept. 2005, roadside verge, near Inistioige, S637373, 1 sh; Co. Carlow, 10 May 2006, woodland edge, S. of Borris, S735457, 2 sh; W. Galway, 22 Apr. 1999, under bark high on tree trunk, near W. end of Kylemore Lough, L759584, 2 sh; W. Galway, 13 May 2004, wooded slopes, NW. of Ballynahinch Castle, L757478, 1 sh; W. Galway, 11 July 2004, on *Hedera*, Pigeon Hole Wood, M13385548, 5 sh; NE. Galway, 6 July 2004, wall covered by *Hedera* at edge of estate woodland, Cargin, M230435, 2 sh; Co. Wicklow, 16 Apr. 2008, waste ground by refuse recycling centre, NW. of Avoca, T198817, 1 sh; Co. Monaghan, 31 Aug. 2007, on trunks of *Fagus* and on *Iris* near stream, Rossmore Forest Park, H653319, 6 sh + bis; Co. Fermanagh, 1 Aug. 2005, woodland, Marble Arch, H121343, 4 sh; Co. Antrim, 9 Oct. 2008, on *Luzula* in steep-sided ravine above river, Glengarriff Forest Park, D212204, 9 spm + 2 bis.

All specimens (except one marked*) Coll. GAH; all are in CGAH; grid references use the British or Irish grids.

Description: Adult shell (Fig. 1E-G) B 7.13-8.12, H 4.06-5.05, U 0-0.40, AB 3.56-4.41, AH 2.87-3.51 mm, with 4.4-4.9 whorls; H/B 0.54-0.62, U/B 0-0.05, AB/B 0.49-0.54; n = 7 (from 3 localities).

Shell conical to rounded-conical, less often depressed-conical, with slightly flattened base. Whorls increasing rapidly, the body whorl relatively large; whorl profile rounded with slight but definite angle just above periphery; sutures moderately deep; the body-whorl not widened or descending near aperture. Aperture broadly oval, except where interrupted by penultimate whorl; peristome thin, mainly plane but reflected at umbilicus which is one-third to fully concealed. When visible, umbilicus very narrow, cylindrical, allowing inside of spire to be seen. Protoconch almost smooth; shell sculpture develops from whorls 1-2 onwards, consisting of (a) obvious irregular low radial ribs, (b) inconspicuous ($\times 20$ magnification) fine spiral grooves, and (c) tiny discontinuous radial lines. Underside of shell with weaker radial ribs and the spiral grooves sometimes lacking. Shell very thin, often weakly calcified so transparent, sometimes slightly thicker so only translucent; usually light brown, sometimes pale brown; periostracum with strong waxy lustre or glossy, underside of shell glossy.

Good published figures include those given in KERNEY & CAMERON (1979: pl. 17 figs 1a-c). The reference to "small, scattered hairs" in the postapical sculpture of fresh shells (SCHILEYKO, 2005: 1960) appears to be erroneous.

Coloration of body variable between localities. Our palest sample of specimens in i.m.s. has exterior of body white or whitish, with black eye-spots and greyish tentacle retractor muscles showing by translucence. Mantle white or whitish with black or blackish band on right-hand side behind front edge. Our darkest preserved sample has blackish extending further around front edge of mantle and also extending back as irregular blackish blotches or irregular bands so much of mantle wall appears dark. Digestive gland inside spire brown. However, ANDERSON (2018) has provided a good photograph of a much darker living Irish specimen with exposed dorsum of body including head and tentacles entirely blackish, the mantle-collar inside shell blackish, roof of mantle cavity pale (seen through semi-transparent shell).

Genital anatomy was investigated in two mature snails collected on 29 Oct. 2008 in Co. Antrim, N. Ireland (see above for details; Fig. 2C-E). The external genital pore was low on the right-

hand flank of the forepart of the body, below and behind the base of the right ommatophore at around one-third of the distance back from the front of the head to the mantle-collar. Genital atrium very short, cylindrical.

Penis long, cylindrical, with thin outer sheath evident; penis narrows markedly at proximal end where distal epiphallus starts; epiphallus very long, muscular, slender, with penial retractor muscle attached at about the middle; the retractor muscle a rather inconspicuous slender strap, passing proximally to attach to the inner wall of the roof of the mantle cavity close to the distal part of the spermoviduct; flagellum long, tapering to very slender apical part. Vas deferens a slender tube passing distally into angle between distal penis and distal vagina before returning proximally alongside vagina to join distal end of spermoviduct.

Vagina short, cylindrical distally; two large muscular dart sacs appear conjoined inside a common sheath attached to middle part of vagina and confluent with it; the inner dart sac somewhat longer than the outer; four mucus glands insert around vagina just proximal to tips of dart sacs; each mucus gland forked close to base into two long cylindrical branches; free oviduct rather short; the bursa copulatrix duct cylindrical, of similar width to free oviduct, passing proximally close alongside the spermoviduct and widening proximally. Reservoir of bursa copulatrix large, elongate, folded *in situ*, resting on proximal part of spermoviduct; reservoir widest and oval at distal (duct) end, extending

proximally as long tapering appendix, which is conical then becoming cylindrical before widening slightly to end in a blunt point (Fig. 2D). Albumen-gland large, curved; common hermaphrodite duct slender, long, convoluted. The retractor muscles for the right ommatophore passed through the angle between the distal penis and distal vagina.

The second individual died with small detached part of a red-brown spermatophore projecting from its genital pore. Dissection revealed that the bursa copulatrix duct contained a long spermatophore internally, clearly visible where the duct outer wall was distended in a loop and also apparent proximally through translucence of the duct wall. The detached part of the spermatophore in transverse section was flattened oval in shape, possessing three high longitudinal lamellae on one side and four or five low sharp ridges on the opposite side (Fig. 2E).

The genital anatomy was figured with a rather schematic drawing (including a dart) by GERMAIN (1930: 252, fig. 199, presumably based on a French specimen) and with more detail by SCHILEYKO (2005: 1961) based on a specimen from Dorset, England. The penial retractor muscle was not found by Schileyko, but was present in our material as noted above. Some uncertainty may exist about the species identity of the *Zenobiellina* genitalia figured by CASTILLEJO (1986: 29-30, including dart and spermatophore) and PUENTE (1994: 649, pl. 121) from N. Spain, especially since our own dissections do not show any clear interspecific differences in genital anatomy.

(Right page) Figure 1. Shells of *Zenobiellina* species (Hygromiidae): A-D, *Z. graminicola* sp. nov.; A-C, from type locality at Desfiladero de la Hermida, Prov. Cantabria, Spain (A, holotype, MNCN; B, C, paratypes, CGAH); D, Covadonga, Prov. Asturias, Spain (paratype, CGAH); E-G, *Z. subrufescens*, E, near Trehursey Bridge, E. Cornwall, Great Britain; F, Rossmore Forest Park, Co. Monaghan, Ireland; G, Upper Tamar Lakes, E. Cornwall, Great Britain (all in CGAH).

(Página derecha) Figura 1. Conchas de especies de *Zenobiellina* (Hygromiidae): A-D, *Z. graminicola* sp. nov.; A-C, de la localidad tipo en Desfiladero de la Hermida, Prov. Cantabria, España (A, holotipo, MNCN; B, C, paratipos, CGAH); D, Covadonga, Prov. Asturias, España (paratipo, CGAH); E-G, *Z. subrufescens*, E, cerca del puente Trehursey, E. Cornwall, Gran Bretaña; F, Rossmore Forest Park, Co. Monaghan, Irlanda; G, Upper Tamar Lakes, E. Cornwall, Gran Bretaña (todos en CGAH).

Zenobiellina graminicola sp. nov. (Figs. 1A-D, 2A-B, 3A-D)

Type material: Holotype (Figs 1A, 2A, B), MNCN reg. no. 15.05/84436 (dry sh with B 9.70 mm & bis kept separately), from type locality, 23 Oct. 2017, Coll. GAH & DTH #E448.

Paratypes: From type locality: 22 May 2001, Coll. GAH, 2 sh; 12 May 2011, Coll. GAH & DTH #E158, 1 sh; 6 July 2017, Coll. GAH & DTH #E446, 59 sh, 2 sh + bis, 11 spm in i.m.s., 5 spm in eth; 23 Oct. 2017, Coll. GAH & DTH #E448, >50 spm in i.m.s.

Other material: 6 July 2017, Covadonga (Prov. Asturias, Spain), N43.3085°, W5.0564° (U.T.M.: 30T 333322/4797135), ca 266 m alt., on herb-rich grassland on banks near castle walls & woodland edges, Coll. GAH & DTH #E447, 41 sh, 3 sh + bis, 5 spm in eth. All paratype specimens are in CGAH.

Type locality: Desfiladero de la Hermida ca 4.5 km SE. along N612 from La Hermida (Prov. Cantabria, Spain), N43.2352°, W4.5767° (U.T.M.: 30T 03721/47881), ca 172 m alt., limestone slopes and crags in gorge, on grassland with herbs (Fig. 3A-D).

Etymology: The epithet *graminicola* is derived from the Latin *gramen* (grass) with suffix *cola* (dweller). Although used adjectivally it is treated as a noun in apposition, hence it has the same form for all genders.

Description: Adult shell (Fig. 1A-D) B 7.92-9.70, H 4.06-5.69, U 0.54-0.94, AB 3.37-4.55, AH 2.67-3.37 mm, with 5.6-6.2 whorls; H/B 0.51-0.59, U/B 0.06-0.10, AB/B 0.43-0.48; n = 7 (all from type locality).

Shell depressed-conical, with somewhat flattened base. Whorls increasing gradually, the body whorl not relatively large; whorl profile rounded with slight but definite angle just above periphery; sutures moderately deep; the body-whorl slightly widened downwards at aperture but not widened upwards. Aperture oval, except where

interrupted by penultimate whorl; peristome thin, mainly plane but reflected at umbilicus which is up to \square (occasionally $\frac{1}{2}$) concealed. Umbilicus narrow, almost cylindrical, allowing inside of spire to be seen. Protoconch almost smooth; shell sculpture develops from whorl 1 onwards, consisting of (a) obvious but fine irregular radial riblets, (b) shallow spiral grooves, that create decussate impression on penultimate whorl and body-whorl, and (c) from whorl 3 onwards, inconspicuous (tiny, $\times 20$ magnification) discontinuous radial lines. Underside of shell with spiral

(Right page) Figure 2. Genital anatomy of *Zenobiellina* species. A: distal genitalia of *Z. graminicola* sp. nov., holotype, from Desfiladero de la Hermida, Prov. Cantabria, Spain; B: same specimen, with vagina and spermoviduct viewed from opposite side; C: *Z. subrufescens*, from Co. Antrim, N. Ireland; D: proximal genitalia of same specimen viewed from opposite side; E: transverse section of detached fragment of spermatophore from different specimen. Abbreviations, a: genital atrium; ag: albumen gland; app: appendage on bursa copulatrix; bc: bursa copulatrix (reservoir); chd: common hermaphrodite duct; dbc: duct of bursa copulatrix; ds: dart sac; e: epiphallus; f: flagellum; mg: mucus gland(s); o: free oviduct; p: penis; (pi: pin); pr: penial retractor muscle; so: spermoviduct; v: vagina; vap: projecting tip of vaginal appendage; vd: vas deferens.

(Página derecha) Figura 2. Anatomía genital de las especies de *Zenobiellina*. A: parte distal del genital de *Z. graminicola* sp. nov., holotipo, de Desfiladero de la Hermida, Prov. Cantabria, España; B: mismo ejemplar, con vagina y espermoviducto vistos desde el lado opuesto; C: *Z. subrufescens*, de Co. Antrim, Irlanda del Norte; D: parte proximal del genital del mismo ejemplar visto desde el lado opuesto; E: sección transversal un fragmento desprendido del espermatóforo de otro ejemplar. Abreviaturas, a: atrio genital; ag: glándula de la albúmina; app: apéndice en la bursa copulatrix; bc: bursa copulatrix (depósito); chd: conducto hermafrodita común; dbc: conducto de la bursa copulatrix; ds: saco del dardo; e: epifalo; f: flagelo; mg: glándulas mucosas; o: oviducto libre; p: pene; (pi: alfiler); pr: músculo retractor del pene; so: espermoviducto; v: vagina; vap: proyección de la punta del apéndice vaginal; vd: vas deferens.

grooves lacking near umbilicus. Shell thin, but calcified, translucent rather than transparent; variable in colour, from whitish to pale brown (most common) or yellowish to (occasionally) light brown, periostracum with waxy lustre, underside of shell glossy.

Exterior of body whitish, rather opaque, sometimes with slight tinge of light brown on tubercles of dorsal foreparts. The black eye spots and grey retractor muscles of the ommatophores visible through translucent skin on preserved specimens. Wide mantle-collar whitish often (8 of 19 specimens checked from type locality) with weak blackish mark behind dorsal edge on inner right-hand side, sometimes accompanied by small dark spots further left. Mantle wall inside shell whitish, often with scattered and somewhat irregular lines of small black (or blackish) spots and an occasional streak of black on outer part. Body inside lower whorls of spire of shell whitish, with scattered black blotches often present (Fig. 3A-D); digestive gland in upper spire of shell brown.

Genital anatomy was investigated in only a single nearly adult snail from the type locality (Fig. 2A, B), but five immatures were also dissected (two from type-locality; three from Covadonga). The external genital pore was a slit at about mid-height on the right-hand side of the forepart of the body, below and behind the base of the right ommatophore. Genital atrium short, with pointed tip of the conical vaginal appendage

projecting from external genital pore in specimen studied.

Penis long, cylindrical, with thin outer sheath evident; its transparency only partly concealing a narrower, white, muscular inner sheath with distinct fold in proximal one-quarter of penis length; penis narrows markedly at proximal end where distal epiphallus starts; epiphallus very long, muscular, slender, with penial retractor muscle attached at one-third distance from distal end; the penis retractor muscle short, attached to inside of outer wall of mantle; flagellum long, tapering to very slender apical part. Vas deferens a slender tube passing distally into angle between distal penis and distal vagina before returning proximally alongside vagina to join distal end of spermoviduct.

Vagina short, cylindrical distally, as already noted, evidently containing a large appendix inside distal part with its pointed tip extending to external genital pore; two large muscular dart sacs appear conjoined inside a common sheath attached to middle part of vagina and confluent with it; the inner dart sac somewhat longer than the outer; four mucus glands insert around vagina just proximal to tips of dart sacs; each mucus gland forked close to base into two long cylindrical branches; free oviduct rather short, curved, leaving proximal end of vagina at right angle, whereas duct of bursa copulatrix continues in line with vagina; the bursa copulatrix duct cylindrical, narrower

(Right page) Figure 3. *Zenobiellina graminicola* sp. nov. and its habitats in northern Spain, photographed on 6 July 2017. A-D: type locality at Desfiladero de la Hermida, Prov. Cantabria, showing (A) natural grassland with *Pteridium* and herbs on rocky limestone slope, and (B-D), immature snails resting on leaves of grasses and underside of leaf of a herb; E: Covadonga, Prov. Asturias, showing managed grassland with abundant herbs, and sampling technique of tapping or shaking vegetation over a sieve.

(Página derecha) Figura 3. *Zenobiellina graminicola* sp. nov. y sus hábitats en el norte de España, fotografiados el 6 de julio de 2017. A-D: localidad tipo en Desfiladero de la Hermida, Prov. Cantabria, que muestra (A) pastizales naturales con *Pteridium* y hierbas en la ladera de piedra caliza rocosa, y (B-D), caracoles inmaduros que descansan en las hojas de los pastos y debajo de la hoja de una hierba; E: Covadonga, Prov. Asturias, mostrando pastizales gestionados con abundantes hierbas, y la técnica de muestreo de golpear o sacudir la vegetación sobre un tamiz.

than free oviduct, passing proximally close alongside the spermoviduct. Reservoir of bursa copulatrix located in tissues adjacent to proximal end of spermoviduct; proximal end of bursa copulatrix broken away in the mature specimen drawn, but evidently elongated in an immature. Proximal genitalia broken off near distal end of spermoviduct, so albumen-gland and common hermaphrodite duct not seen in specimen drawn, but observed in immatures. The retractor muscles for the right ommatophore

passed between the distal penis and distal vagina.

Overall, the distal genitalia appear similar to those of *Z. subrufescens*. The mucus gland branches are longer in the *Z. graminicola*, but this may reflect the larger body size in this species. The penial retractor muscle of *Z. graminicola* was shorter than that found in our *Z. subrufescens*, but its length varies intraspecifically in other Helicacea so more material needs to be studied to check whether the difference is consistent.

DISCUSSION

Z. graminicola differs from *Z. subrufescens* mainly in shell characters. Although all fresh shells that are more than about half-grown can readily be identified to species, the following quantitative comparisons are based only on mature shells. *Z. graminicola* has a larger umbilicus (6-10% of shell breadth, cf. 0-5%), more numerous whorls (5.6-6.2, cf. 4.4-4.9) and a proportionately narrower body-whorl resulting in a smaller aperture (AB/B 43-48%, cf. 49-54%). Another consistent but less obvious difference is the much stronger development of spiral microsculpture on the periostracum in *Z. graminicola*. Also, most shells of *Z. graminicola* are thicker (translucent, not transparent), pale brown rather than light brown, and on average they have lower spires and less rounded apertures.

The overall geographical range of *Z. subrufescens* has been regarded as extending from N. Ireland and Scotland southwards locally through W. France to N. Spain (e.g. KERNEY & CAMERON, 1979; FALKNER, RIPKEN & FALKNER, 2002; CADEVALL & OROZCO, 2016). Recognition of *Zenobiellina graminicola* as a second species of the genus from NW. Spain that has sometimes been overlooked there as *Z. subrufescens* necessitates a reassessment of the range and habitat preferences of *Z. subrufescens*, at least in Spain, and perhaps also in S. France.

All records from Spain of *Zenobiellina* appear to be relatively recent, the oldest noted in the compilation by

PUENTE (1994: 646) being from Prov. Navarra by LARRAZ, BECH & CAMPOY (1981), with more in the same province given by LARRAZ (1982). CASTILLEJO (1986: 28, 58 map 7) recorded five localities in northern and western Galicia. By the early 1990s, ALTONAGA ET AL. (1994: 290, 487) were able to map numerous additional records from N. Spain, extending from Prov. Lugo to Prov. Navarra, albeit with a distinct gap in range because the genus appears to be absent from most of the Basque Country. Although all of the records were presented as *Z. subrufescens*, they need to be critically reassessed since it is likely that *Z. graminicola* has sometimes been confused with that species in the past. However, PUENTE (1994: pl. 185 row 1) illustrated an undoubted shell of *Z. subrufescens* s. str. from Kakueta, Prov. Palencia, and CASTILLEJO'S (1986: 28) description of shells from Galicia as "delgadas y frágiles, de color ambarino" are strongly suggestive of this species alone.

Some of the classic literature for Britain and Ireland gave the habitat of *Z. subrufescens* only as "woods" (MILLER, 1822: 379; JEFFREYS, 1904: 205) or "damp woods" (GRAY, 1857: 132). KERNEY (1999: 191) described it as a "snail of old, broad-leaved woodland ... especially in moist sheltered situations" but added that "It is also found in more open (but always relatively wild) places, in ancient hedgerows, among rocks and

sea cliffs, on lush grassy roadside banks, and occasionally in marshes". He demonstrated a marked decline since the nineteenth century in eastern and central England, where it is rare and possibly more closely restricted to wooded sites.

Our own records from Great Britain and Ireland listed above show it frequently occurs in other more open habitats (only 2 of 8 records from Cornwall were in woodland; whereas 11 of 14 from Ireland were in woodland, coppiced woodland or wooded gardens), at least in these regions which both have higher annual rainfall than that of E. and C. England. Older records by DTH from W. Scotland (around Oban, Main Argyll) were also from both woodland and more open sites, as were others from scattered locations across western England and Wales (specimens in NMW.Z). However, even in open sites the species was often collected from woody vegetation such as foliage of bushes or ivy (*Hedera*). Among sites with no bushes though, a Cornish record (from Upper Tamar Lakes) was from long herb-rich grassland on a grassy bank at the edge of a reservoir, showing that numerically strong populations do live in sites lacking bushes and trees.

Our two sites for *Z. graminicola* described above both had large and extensive populations living in herb-rich grassland lacking trees and without bushes (Covadonga) or with only a few sparse bushes (Desfiladero de la Hermida) (Fig. 3A). The Covadonga

populations were at least partly on a bank of grassland managed by mowing, with the edges of woodland/plantations close by (Fig. 3E). The Desfiladero de la Hermida site was in grassland where grazing may impede colonisation by saplings and bushes. Both locations are likely to have high humidity because of the high regional rainfall and shelter respectively provided in the ravine of a small river and between a woodland edge and a tall old building. Study of more sites with *Z. graminicola* and of Spanish sites for *Z. subrufescens* is of course needed to establish the full range of habitats each of them occupies and whether these do differ consistently between the species. However, it is noteworthy that at both of our sites with *Z. graminicola* it was found living only on grasses (Fig. 3B, C), herbs (Fig. 3D) and *Pteridium* in open grassland. Searches for it were unsuccessful inside closely adjacent groves of trees or *Corylus* scrub and on the trunks, branches and foliage of bushes and saplings at their edges in situations similar to those where *Z. subrufescens* would be expected.

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